

Hybrid Fuel Cell for Pulse Power Applications

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Abstract

A hybrid fuel cell demonstrated pulse power capability. It successfully ran a pulse power load simulation synonymous with electronics and communications equipment. The hybrid consisted of a 25 W Proton Exchange Membrane Fuel Cell (PEMFC) stack in parallel with a 70 farad capacitor assembly.

A cyclic regime of 18.0 W for 2 minutes followed by 2.5 W for 18 minutes was chosen as the basic test regime. The operating potential cut-off voltage for pass/failure was set to 3.0 V. At room temperature (23-25 °C), the PEMFC alone could not successfully power the baseline regime previously described. The PEMFC operating potential dropped below 3.0 V within 10 seconds. The hybrid continuously powered the cyclic regime for 25 hours. The hybrid's operating potential never reached the voltage cut-off, even during the high load of 18.0 W. The tests were aborted after 25 hours of operation with no signs of output degradation, suggesting that continuous operation is possible.

Introduction

Due to their high energy density, fuel cells are being actively investigated for use in portable electronics and communications equipment. Besides a high energy density, the power capabilities of fuel cells are of interest. Fuel cells demonstrate good power capability during continuous operation. However, the response of PEMFC to instantaneous power demands is relatively poor. It often requires up to 5 minutes to reach an operational steady state at a constant power load, during which individual cells of the stack become highly polarized. This polarized state is detrimental to the PEMFC stack. In many instances involving instantaneous power increases, the PEMFC's operating potential does not recover. This translates into fuel cells alone having great difficulty handling periods of high power pulses. The development of power assistance for PEM fuel cells is; therefore, of great interest.

Applications for electrochemical capacitors are being sought because of their high power density. Fully packaged electrochemical capacitors have shown specific power densities of up to 2000 W/kg and specific energy density of up to 4.5 Whr/kg^[1,2].

The utilization of such electrochemical capacitors in the power assistance of fuel cell stacks would allow for a system that has the energy density advantage of fuel cells and the high power output capability of electrochemical capacitors.

Experimental

All testing was conducted with a Techware Automated Battery Cycler (ABC) and a Tenney Jr. environmental chamber. The ABC is capable of constant power cycling to a maximum of 5.0 A. During testing, the operating voltage and current were recorded at every change of 0.1 V. This record increment guaranteed good data fit.

A 25 watt Proton Exchange Membrane (PEM) fuel stack of 6 cells was used. The nominal potential is 4.0 V. The stack used ambient air to supply both the reactant oxygen and the air used as the heat sink (coolant air). The coolant air removed the heat energy produced by the electrochemical reaction. Zero grade (99.999%) compressed hydrogen, regulated to 1 psig, was the fuel. The cell stack design is dead ended. A purge device was installed to the stack which provided for purging to open air 1 second every 5 minutes. This prevented the build-up of contaminants that eventually reduce stack's performance.

The electrochemical capacitors used in the hybrid are commercially available Panasonic "Gold" power series capacitors. They are rated at 2.5 V and 10 farads capacitance. These are single cell capacitors with carbon electrodes and organic electrolyte. The capacitance measured on the discharge of a single capacitor at 100 mA was 14.2 farads with a 95% charge to discharge

efficiency. These capacitors are characterized by low leakage current ($80\mu\text{A}$ - measured following 5 hours of charging), stable open circuit voltage (after 48 hours from the initial 2.5 V the potential dropped to 2.27 V), and relatively low equivalent series resistance ($72\text{ m}\Omega$ - measured at 1 kHz). Twenty-eight of these capacitors were connected in series and in parallel into the bank of capacitors. This capacitor bank has a nominal capacitance of 70 farads and voltage of 5.0 V. The total capacitance of the bank measured at charge/discharge cycles under constant current of 1.0 A was 114.5/107.3 farads at voltage of 5.0 V and 114.9/114.4 farads at voltage of 6.0 V; respectively. The internal resistance of the capacitor bank measured from the voltage drop during charge and discharge cycle was $25\text{ m}\Omega$. This capacitor bank was connected in parallel to the fuel cell stack.

The tests were initially conducted at 4.4 °C, room temperature (23-25 °C), and 37.7 °C. The limits of the PEMFC alone at 18.0 W continuous power at the three temperatures was quantified. Performance of the hybrid was measured at various radio simulation transmit and receive duration at 4.4 °C and room temperature (RT). Tests were designed to last 25.0 hours continuous. Operating voltage and current, and internal stack temperatures were monitored and recorded.

Results

The 25 W PEMFC stack by itself could not power the high load pulse of high/low power cyclic regimes. The baseline profile of 18.0 W for 2 minutes followed by 2.5 W for 18 minutes, for example, was a great strain on the stack alone. During the 18.0 W pulse the stack operating potential substantially dropped and became very erratic. Within 10 seconds, the stack voltage fell below the 3.0 V cut-off voltage.

A 70 farad capacitor bank connected in parallel with the 25 W PEMFC successfully powered the baseline regime described above. Figure 1 shows the system baseline curve at RT with and without the 70 farad capacitor attached. It clearly shows that without the capacitor, the PEMFC can not power the 18.0 W load. During the first ten cycles (200 minutes) the hybrid successfully powered the entire regime. The

operating voltage never dropped below 3.0 V; even during the high 18.0 W load. Following the 2 minute high load sequence of the 11th cycle, the capacitor was disconnected from the fuel cell. This is denoted by region A in Figure 1. At this instance, the PEMFC alone was successfully powering the low load section of cycle 11. Following the 18 minutes of low load, the PEMFC alone failed to power the 18.0W pulse of cycle 12 (region B). The stack potential immediately fell below 3.0 V and never recovered. This demonstrates the inability of the fuel cell alone to maintain operating potential above 3.0 V during pulse power operation.

Figure 2 displays the hybrid limits at constant power discharge of 18.0 W (worst case scenario). Tests were run at 4.4 °C, RT, and 37.7 °C. At 4.4 °C and RT, hybrid performance clearly followed the effects of ambient temperature on concentration polarization. Figure 2 shows that continuous 18.0 W RT operation can be achieved utilizing the hybrid configuration. This data, combined with the fact that it often requires up to 5 minutes for a non-hybrid PEMFC to recover to an operational steady state when a power load is instantaneously applied, demonstrates the benefit of the hybrid configuration.

A PEMFC becomes excessively polarized when a power load is instantaneously applied. This is due mainly to mass transfer limitations within the membrane of the PEMFC. The hybrid configuration allows for a gradual increase in mass transfer within the membrane allowing for the establishment of steady state diffusion without subjecting the stack to deep polarization. This is a result of the capacitors assuming the initial load and the fuel cell gradually providing the required power as the capacitors' voltage drops. At cold temperatures the power handling device of the hybrid requires higher capacity (capacitance) to overcome the additional transport resistance introduced with temperature.

Figure 2 also shows the results at lower ambient temperatures, where chemical activity is reduced; therefore, increasing the internal resistance and reducing performance. At 37.7 °C; however, the six membrane electrode assemblies (MEA's) of the PEMFC stack quickly "dried out" due to moisture loss. At this

stage the proton conductivity was significantly reduced; lowering fuel cell performance. The MEA's were rehydrated by 4.0 A continuous discharge for 12 hours. Due to the unreliability at 37.7 °C, evaluation at this temperature was discontinued.

At 4.4 °C, the hybrid failed to successfully power any regime consisting of transmit load (18.0 W) durations of 2 minutes or longer. Figure 2 shows this. At 4.4 °C and 18.0 W continuous discharge, the hybrid "lasted" for slightly more than 100 seconds. For up to 1 minute transmit durations; the hybrid successfully powered regimes with the receive period as low as 3 minutes (2.5 W). Figure 3 displays this. The hybrid successfully powered the cyclic regime of 1 minute high load (18.0 W) followed by 3 minutes low load (2.5 W) for 25 hours continuous. This means that the PEMFC stack required only 3 minutes to recharge the 70 farad capacitor assembly to a charge state sufficient to "assist" the stack for the next high load pulse of 18.0 W.

At RT, the hybrid successfully powered cyclic scenarios consisting of transmit durations of up to 3 minutes. Figure 2 demonstrates this. At RT and 18.0 W continuous discharge, the hybrid capacity was enough for approximately 250 seconds of operation down to 3.0V. Transmit durations of 1, 2, and 3 minutes required receive lengths of as low as 1.5, 3, and 4.5 minutes; respectively. This means, for example, that for 3 minutes transmit (18.0 W) the PEMFC stack required 4.5 minutes of receive (2.5 W) period to recharge the capacitors for the next cycle.

Figures 4 and 4A show the hybrid potential during a 2 minute transmit and a 3 minute receive cycle. Figure 4 shows the full 25 hour test and figure 4A represents the last 12 cycles. Figures 5 and 5A show the hybrid potential during a 3 minute transmit and a 4.5 minute receive cycle. As with figures 4 and 4A, Figure 5 represents the full 25 hour test and figure 5A only the last 12 cycles. These figures show that the hybrid was able to successfully power the corresponding regimes for 25 hours continuously. Note that the hybrid will run any cyclic scenario with transmit:receive ratio of

1:1.5 for up to 3 minutes transmit (18.0 W). This specific duty cycle provides sufficient charging time for the capacitor assembly. This allowed for continuous hybrid operation.

Testing of the hybrid performance at 37.7 °C showed that dehydration of the fuel cell stack is the major limitation to its performance. Two individual runs were attempted with the fuel cell at 37.7 °C. These experiments were conducted to determine if the hybrid configuration could overcome the conductivity limitation of the PEMFC due to "dry out" conditions caused by high temperature operation. Duty cycles of 1 minute transmit followed by 9 minutes receive and 1 minute transmit followed by 30 minutes receive were used. Figure 6 shows the hybrid discharge voltage curve at 1 minute transmit (18.0 W) followed by 9 minutes receive (2.5 W). The result of the 1 and 9 test shows that the PEMFC did not have sufficient time to recharge the capacitor for the next pulse. When the 1 and 30 test was performed, the results were similar. The operating potential is significantly lower than at both 4.4 °C and RT. The potential of the hybrid quickly fell below the 3.0 volt cutoff at the start of the second cycle. This is all result of the MEA's of each cell of the PEMFC stack drying out, thus drastically affecting its performance.

Conclusions

Unlike the fuel cell alone, the hybrid of PEMFC stack and capacitor assembly successfully powered high pulse loads at different duty cycles. During high power pulses, the capacitor assembly assisted the PEMFC stack. At low power periods, the PEMFC stack powered the load and at the same time recharged the capacitor for the next cycle. In this way, the hybrid delivered both high energy and high power density required by the load.

References

1. US Department of Energy, "Capacitor State-of-the-Art Overview", Proceedings IAPG Meeting, 9-11 May 1995, Newport, RI

2. T.C. Murphy, G.H. Cole and P.B. Davis, "Temperature Effects on Ultracapacitor Performance: INEL Test Results", Proceedings of the 5th International Seminar on Double Layer Capacitors and Similar Energy Storage Devices, 4-6 December 1995, Boca Raton, FL.

Figure 1. System (30 Volt PSMPC & 70 Farad Capacitor) Baseline Curve

Figure 2. 18.0 Watts Continuous Discharge.

Figure 3. 4.4°C Hybrid Discharge. Cyclic Profile of 1 Minute Transmit followed by 3 Minutes Receive.

Figure 4. RT Hybrid Discharge. Cyclic Profile of 2 Minutes Transmit followed by 3 Minutes Receive.

Figure 4A. Last Twelve Cycles (1 Hour) of Figure 4.

Figure 5. RT Hybrid Discharge. Cyclic Profile of 3 Minutes Transmit followed by 4.5 Minutes Receive.

Figure 5A. Last Twelve Cycles (1.5 Hours) of Figure 5.

Figure 6. Typical Hybrid Performance at 37.7°C.